

Milestone: M3.5: Proof-of-concept implementation of optimisations in a workflow management system

Lead Participant: UFR

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Due: 31 January 2026 (24)

Date Of Completion: 30/04/2026

Means of Verification

- [Making Galaxy Greener with the Job Cache](#)
- [Using Galaxy webhooks to nudge users toward better tools](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Whilst the project requirements were met within the projected timeframe, completion of this report was delayed to align with the production of dissemination content (2 blogposts) that provide additional value as project outputs.

Project participants & others

- Nicola Soranzo (EI)
- Björn Grüning (DE)
- Paul De Geest (BE)
- Anthony Bretaudeau (FR)
- Uku Raudvere (EE)
- Martin Cech (CZ)

Next action steps

- Content-based input hashing to improve reuse opportunities.
- Quantifying avoided emissions by combining cache metadata with Galaxy's carbon reporting framework.

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